

THE POLITICS BEHIND CORONAVIRIUS PANDEMIC

Coronavirus, a deadly airborne and infectious disease that started in Wuhan, China late December in 2019, starting with little infections but has slowly grown into a worldwide pandemic with more than a million infections globally and more than 40 000 deaths, 80% of which are in Europe. It was declared a pandemic in March by the World Health Organization- WHO. Symptoms which include fever, cough, difficulty in breathing etc. according to W. H. O, once one feels the symptoms he or she should go into isolation for 2 to 14 days. Transmissions occur through handshakes, droplets from infected persons through sneezing or cough, that's why people tend to give to give an awkward look when you sneeze without covering your mouth. It's by analysis the worst to hit the world.

Now that we have known little about the virus, the primary theme in this work is the politics that's being played amidst the outbreak of the virus. The United States has accused China of creating the virus as a weapon to severely deal with the Chinese Muslims who are facing what I call "silent discrimination". It was created as a tool to eliminate them, but unfortunately they couldn't handle its effect. In reverse, China also accused the US for being responsible for the outbreak using its soldiers who according to China imported it to the Peoples Republic. The question is, where they- US soldiers did, contact the virus from? Leaving that unanswered, what's more strange is the relatively low number of fatalities in China.

Italy and Spain having the most deaths so far. Italy having more than 12 000 deaths and Spain 10 000 deaths are the two worst hit countries with the United States being the third with more than 5 000 deaths and more than a 100 00 infections. Donald Trump, weeks ago called it the 'Chinese Virus' when asked why, he said because it's from China. Definitely he must have known something related to its outbreak that's why he and the Chinese government were pointing accusing fingers. It was said to have begun from the city of Wuhan in China, what we weren't told was how it broke out or how it started spreading or who were the first to contact and how they contacted it. If the minimum number of days for isolation is two days and maximum being 14 days, how then are there thousands of deaths daily? Back to China, at the very first sign of a problem, and at a time when officials had their only realistic chance of stopping the spread of the virus, the leaders of the Communist Party of China instead chose to suppress the reports of doctors who sought to sound the alarm. Evidence of the outbreak was destroyed and facts denied. A national epidemic has now become a global pandemic. At the first instance, Doctor Li Wenliang, the doctor censured for trying to warn his colleagues about the outbreak. He told his fellow medical professionals about the virus in a group chat on 30 December. He was accused of rumor mongering and officials played down the risks. Before he died, he was interviewed by the New York Times where he said "I think it should have been a lot better. There should be transparency" after Dr Li's death, "we want freedom of speech" was trending on Chinese social media for several hours before the posts were deleted. The United States called it a

hoax in the initial stages of its outbreak.

Coming back to Africa, in Nigeria, there have been daily reported index of the virus made by the NCDC. Everyone seems to panic whenever news drops in concerning the outbreak in the country. With reportedly 190 cases, more than 20 discharged and 2 deaths. These figures seem to be either lower or more likely higher than they seem. One thing to point out clear is that cases are different from infections. Cases are those have been observed to be showing symptoms of the virus and have been isolated or quarantined. However, infections are those who have being tested positive and showing severe manifestations of the virus and are being hospitalized. There haven't being clear distinction on cases and infections. The government has being criticized for acting too slow amidst the outbreak in the country, airports and borders were not shut on time and there have being accusations about the poor distribution of relief of materials to the less privileged. I quote "if electricity bills can reach every house, then relief materials should reach every house" funds that were released by the government and even donations are more than 10 billion naira. We haven't seen significant usage of those funds. Our policy makers must start telling the truth to avoid rapid spread of the virus.

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